

PP: *Pseudocohnilembus persalinus*

UM: *Uronema marinum*

CB: *Cafeteria burkhardae*

PF: *Paraphysomonas foraminifera*

PI: *Paraphysomonas imperforata*

PSP: *Paraphysomonas* sp.

File summary:

1. [Approximate number of generation.xlsx](#)

Data on the approximate number of generations of the six investigated protozoa under their warmest selection condition during the long-term adaptation. The number was estimated by the initial and final cell density during each six-day transfer.

2. [ESD.xlsx](#)

Cell size in terms of equivalent spherical diameter (ESD) of the six investigated protozoa at an elevated environmental temperature (25°C for PI and 31°C for other species) after being selected by different temperature scenarios.

3. [GR.csv](#)

Growth rates (GR) of the six investigated protozoa at different assay temperatures under different temperature selection conditions.

4. [Growth monitoring during adaptation.csv](#)

Growth rates of PP, UM, PF, PI, and PSP in the exponential period under the warmest selection condition during the long-term adaptation.

5. [IR.csv](#)

Ingestion rates (IR) of the six investigated protozoa at different assay temperatures under different temperature selection conditions.

6. [RR.csv](#)

Respiration rates (RR) of the six investigated protozoa at different assay temperatures under different temperature selection conditions.